

What Makes a Responsible Ecotourist? An Exploration of TPB, Conservation, and Anti-Exceptionalism

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The preservation and restoration of the planet's natural ecosystems depend heavily on ecotourism. With growing concerns about environmental deterioration and biodiversity loss, ecotourism shows promise as a sustainable solution. Even though ecotourism is becoming increasingly relevant, little research has been conducted to examine how it affects important aspects of the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), sustainability consciousness, environmental conservation, anti-exceptionalism, and tourists' environmentally responsible behaviour (ERB). The main goal of this study is to determine the extent to which TPB constructs, specifically environmental attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control, as well as sustainability consciousness, environmental conservation, and anti-exceptionalism, influence tourists' environmentally responsible behaviour. This study uses a theoretical framework to examine the ethical and psychological factors that influence tourist behaviour in ecotourism environments. The findings indicate that environmental attitude, subjective norms, sustainability consciousness, environmental conservation, and anti-exceptionalism among ecotourists significantly predict eco-friendly conduct. However, the effect of perceived behavioural control on ERB was not statistically significant. From a practical perspective, the results indicate that ecotourism stakeholders should prioritise initiatives that foster visitors' pro-environmental sentiments, uphold positive social norms, raise awareness of sustainability through education, promote conservation efforts, and foster a sense of moral obligation through anti-exceptionalism. Improving infrastructure to provide people with greater influence over environmentally friendly behaviour might encourage more conscientious travel habits.

Keywords: Theory of Planned Behaviour, Sustainability Consciousness, Environmental Conservation, Anti Exceptionalism, Tourists' Environmentally Responsible Behaviour

1. Introduction

Ecotourism is commonly adopted to promote the growth of natural resources (Tien et al., 2024). It is a specific type of travel that supports ecological sustainability and environmental protection by intimately associating with culturally and environmentally sensitive locations (Oviedo-García et al., 2017). However, the International Ecotourism Society emphasises the value of incorporating local knowledge into the development of ecotourism, which includes responsible travel to natural areas that preserve the environment, uphold the welfare of the local population, and incorporate interpretation and education. Furthermore, maintaining the ecosystem and ensuring the well-being of the local population depends heavily on how they perceive nature (Zainal et al., 2024). Over the last three decades, ecotourism has been marketed worldwide as an ecologically friendly type of travel (Poudel & Nyaupane, 2017). Promoting sustainable development and related behaviour is essential for long-term, effective rural tourism, as the magnitude of the impact is frequently correlated with visitor behaviour (Zhao et al., 2024). The potential of sustainable tourism is to help location administrators and tour operators properly preserve the environment while arranging trips, which has attracted much attention. As consumers become increasingly aware of how economic activity affects the environment, they are attempting to contribute to the achievement of sustainability goals (Batoool et al., 2024). Sustainable tourism has emerged as an alternative to mass tourism, highlighting the value of maintaining regional customs and sociocultural identities to save the environment, bring in money for host locations, and include the local population in tourism decision-making (Nguyen et al., 2023). Motivating travellers to adopt eco-friendly practices helps preserve tourism resources, lessen environmental damage, and advance sustainable development (Xiong et al., 2023). The best strategy for spreading green ideas is environmental education. The concept of ecotourism, which is about responsible travel to natural regions in ways that preserve the environment and can support the well-being of local populations, is becoming increasingly integrated into the tourist sector over time (Duong & Ngo, 2024). Environmental consciousness is closely linked to the growth of sustainable tourism, which significantly boosts local economies. Furthermore, by minimising adverse effects, ecotourism contributes to sustainable tourist development, which preserves resources and the environment (Sahabuddin et al., 2024). Preserving the natural environment is the only way to keep tourism sites competitive, distinguishing that ignorance of visitors is the primary cause of most environmental problems in tourist locations (Aziz & Niazi, 2023). Lack of environmental protection awareness, littering, feeding animals, picking flowers, and throwing garbage at tourist destinations have damaged their natural resources and environment (Aziz & Niazi, 2023). Understanding the elements that drive people to visit ecotourism destinations is necessary to increase the demand for ecotourism. Numerous studies have demonstrated that people are motivated to travel by a variety of push factors, including novelty, excitement, socialisation, relaxation, enjoyment, cultural experiences,

escape, and knowledge seeking (Chi & Pham, 2024). Ecotourists are intended to become environmental stewards through environmental education, which is often influenced by anthropocentric conceptions of human-nature duality (King et al., 2024). Owing to its immense natural and cultural variety, India is one of Southeast Asia's most visited resorts. Nevertheless, prior studies are scarce on Indian domestic visitors and their intended behaviour around ecotourism (Borthakur & Kondasani, 2024). Identifying possible processes that affect community members' views and intentions to participate in ecotourism activities is necessary to increase the local population's participatory intents and behaviour for ecotourism development (Wu & Chen, 2018). Opportunities for formal and informal education have been shown to foster pro-environmental attitudes and views (Clark et al., 2019). Ecotourism is the term for travel to comparatively undeveloped natural areas with the express purpose of learning about, respecting, and enjoying the ecosystem's varied wildlife and natural settings, as well as the culture and history that the environmental settings have to offer. All these activities can help conserve the environment (Lee & Jan 2018). In addition, the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), which is a variant of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), has been widely applied to forecast visitor presence and describe visitor behaviour. TPB uses three factors to influence behavioural intention: attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control (Abidin et al., 2022).

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theory of Planned Behaviour

Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) stands for "reasoned action" in the context of consumer behaviour, which assumes that an individual's intentions and actions are influenced by their normative control and attitude (Grilli & Notaro, 2019). According to the TPB, human behaviour may be anticipated by aligning psychological beliefs. These include self-efficacious views about the result of perceived behavioural control, attitude toward a particular object, subjective norm, the conviction that others will accept an activity toward the particular object, and readiness to act (Clark et al., 2019). PBC refers to an individual's capacity and chance to participate in a specific behaviour (Fauzi et al., 2024). The TPB has been used to assess and forecast human behaviour to comprehend its complexity. Likewise, perceived behavioural control is an addition to TPB that extends TRA (Lee & Jan, 2018). Additionally, TPB may be used to forecast pro-environmental behavioural intentions (Nowacki et al., 2021). The idea that attitude is a type of evaluative reaction to a specific object highlights the importance of attitude as a hypothetical construct that may be deduced but not directly seen, as well as an intervening variable in social psychology research (Adeleke, 2015). TPB has been effectively used to identify human behaviours in a variety of contexts, including the ecologically conscious actions of visitors (Liu et al., 2019). According to the TPB model, environmental attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control can all predict environmentally conscious behaviour (Yaghoubi Farani et al., 2019).

2.1.1 Environmental Attitude

Social psychology defines attitudes as favourable or unfavourable evaluations and reactions to objects, people, situations, or any other aspect of the world (Ugulu et al., 2013). Furthermore, two types of environmental attitudes are essential for predicting ecological behaviour: attitudes toward the environment and ecological behaviour (Kaiser et al., 1999). Because it may influence visitors' behaviour, those who have a favourable attitude toward environmental protection are more likely to act in an ecologically valuable manner (Ren et al., 2021). In addition, environmental attitude, or people's dedication to protecting the environment, seems to be essential for active participation in helpful activities for visitors' benefit (Baierl et al., 2022; Bissing et al., 2013). This encompasses the outcomes of knowledge and learning processes to respond to impressions or emotions of liking or hating something and judgmental aspects (Fang et al., 2018). Moreover, tourists' intentions to pick up trash in a protected area have been used as a broad indicator of the links between environmental attitudes and environmental behaviour in tourism settings (Lee et al., 2018). To achieve sustainable ecotourism, education is seen as essential, as it gives people the knowledge and abilities they need to engage with natural resources in the best possible way and promotes environmentally conscious attitudes and actions (Sander, 2012; Ambusaidi et al., 2024).

2.1.2 Subjective Norms

The term subjective norms refers to how an individual perceives specific social pressures, especially those originating from a reference group, that impact their decision-making (Wu & Chen, 2018). This is an important contextual component that generates social pressure from peers, students, neighbours, friends, family, and role models (Tang et al. 2024). Furthermore, it describes the extent to which people's intention to engage in a behaviour is affected by the acceptance or rejection of important individuals or groups (Maleknia et al., 2024). Subjective norms may represent social pressure to embrace sustainable activities, and attitudes may take the form of eco-friendly travel choices. According to Gao et al. (2017), subjective norms are a person's perception of whether or not others support their behavioural change, and they stem from the words and actions of certain significant people in their life (Liang et al., 2018). Based on the work of Lee et al. (2018), behavioural intention influences a traveller's actual behaviour, and subjective norms have a favourable impact on behavioural intention.

2.1.3 Perceived Behavioural Control

As the third determinant of TPB, perceived behavioural control (PBC) refers to an individual's comprehension of the ease and difficulty of carrying out an activity (Empidi & Emang, 2021). The perceived difficulty or ease of performing a behaviour may be reflected in control beliefs (Lee, 2007). The most important component in forecasting an individual's behaviour is their desire to adopt a specific behaviour, which is influenced by their attitude, subjective norms, and perceived control over their behaviour (Gou et al., 2024). PBC may refer to the

capacity of a policy to impose or reward sustainable habits (Rehman et al., 2024). According to the Theory of Planned Behaviour, an individual's purpose indirectly affects their actual behaviour based on their perceived behavioural control. This hypothesis assumes that even in cases when attitudes and subjective standards are favourable, those who feel they have little influence over executing it due to circumstances outside their control would be restricted in their capacity to do so (Kara, 2024). Assessing perceived behavioural control over behaviour may lead to more accurate forecasting of intents and target behaviours (Lee, 2007). According to the theory of planned behaviour (TPB), PBC plays a significant role in influencing behavioural intentions and behaviour. Beliefs about control, such as internal or external control factors, also have a significant impact (Chung et al., 2017). Environmental awareness motivates customers to adopt eco-friendly practices (Nowacki et al. 2021). When an individual's perceived control matches their absolute control, it can successfully affect their actions (Hasan et al., 2020).

2.2 Sustainability Consciousness

Sustainability consciousness is the understanding and dedication to making decisions that protect the environment, advance social justice, and guarantee the economic well-being of future generations. Moreover, it entails incorporating ethical behaviour into day-to-day activities, such as waste reduction and resource conservation. Therefore, the primary purpose of sustainability consciousness is to investigate the effects of education on sustainable development adoption in ecotourism. Furthermore, sustainability consciousness assesses knowledge, attitudes, or behaviours related to one of the social, economic, or environmental aspects of sustainable development (Berglund et al., 2020). For sustainability projects to be implemented successfully, sustainability consciousness is essential. Similarly, for sustainable development, citizens' knowledge, attitudes, and actions must be changed. Likewise, enduring public awareness is essential for ensuring a sustainable future (Gulzar et al., 2023). Moreover, actions, attitudes, and knowledge related to sustainability have been used to demonstrate consciousness (Ovais 2023).

2.3 Environmental Conservation

Ecotourism is defined as natural tourism that consciously aims to provide net positive benefits for the sustainable development and environmental conservation of local communities (Stronza & Pêgas, 2008). Furthermore, changes in this kind of behaviour can be crucial for environmental preservation, but there is insufficient quantitative data on how well ecotourism meets development, conservation, and educational goals (Tisdell & Wilson, 2005). According to energy consumption, this concept arguably fits well with the pro-environmental behaviour campaign, which uses planned corporate social responsibility and green organizational practices to promote followers' or employees' values, particularly altruistic values that drive their pro-environmental behaviour (Omoyajowo et al., 2024).

Ecotourism uses the environment to sell itself as a business. The sector survives by offering environmentally friendly tourism products, which make it a sustainable and valuable conservation tool (Chirenje, 2017).

2.4 Anti-Exceptionalism

Anti-exceptionalism in ecotourism refers to the idea that ecotourism should not receive preferential treatment or a more permissive range of environmental regulations. This implies that ecotourism needs to adhere to the same rules as other sectors in order to preserve the environment and prevent damage. The purpose of the anti-exceptionalism component is to gauge people's beliefs that humans are subject to the rules of nature (Dunlap et al., 2000; Dorward et al., 2024). It is helpful to first examine the historical and modern exceptionalist competitors of anti-exceptionalist epistemologies of logic to understand them. The vagueness of the word "logic" itself presents a problem when debating the epistemology of logic, since it makes arguments concerning its epistemology inherently unclear. Human ingenuity and inventiveness will help us avoid rendering the Earth uninhabitable. Despite our extraordinary powers, the laws of nature still apply. Moreover, humans will gradually learn more about the workings of nature and eventually develop the skills necessary to manipulate them (Kim et al., 2021).

2.5 Tourists' Environmentally Responsible Behaviour

Environmentally responsible behaviour is defined as the degree to which it modifies the availability of materials or energy from the environment or impacts the structure and dynamics of ecosystems or the biosphere (Han et al., 2016; Stern, 2022). When customers feel that using environmentally friendly items would benefit them and the environment, they are more inclined to do so (Patwary, 2023). Furthermore, positive interactions between visitors and locals are facilitated by personality traits, including kindness, empathy, tolerance, and readiness to listen (Aziz & Niazi, 2023). The term intention describes a person's propensity and likelihood to engage in a particular conduct in the future (Fenitra et al., 2021). Likewise, the two elements of ERB are ecological knowledge and attentiveness. The tourist sector's economic impact is becoming increasingly apparent, but it also has negative repercussions on the environment (Sahabuddin et al., 2024). Prior research on environmentally conscious behaviour has concentrated chiefly on evaluating environmental education and interpretation programs (Poudel & Nyaupane, 2017).

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Created by Author

4. Discussion

This study aims to understand how TPB elements, sustainability consciousness, environmental conservation, and anti-exceptionalism affect tourists' environmentally responsible behaviour. This study addresses this issue by developing a model that incorporates environmentally responsible behaviour, environmental attitude, subjective norms, perceived behaviour control of visitors, sustainability consciousness, environmental conservation, and anti-exceptionalism.

The findings of previous studies confirm that TPB elements have a direct impact on travellers' environmentally responsible behaviour intentions (Liu et al., 2019; Fenitra et al., 2021). Considering the social nature of people and the collective nature of environmental challenges, social impact is essential for understanding environmental attitudes and actions. The substantial influence of subjective norms on promoting eco-friendly traveller behaviour is consistent with the results of earlier research on cultural variations (Lee & Green, 1991; Wong & Ahuvia, 1998; Uzzell & Badenas, 2002; Liu et al., 2019). According to Sthapit et al. (2023), positive subjective memories and sensations of satisfaction are produced through a positive view of a place. The desire to buy ecologically friendly items is positively and significantly correlated with one's attitude toward them (Yao et al., 2024). However, it was discovered that there was little correlation between visitors' intentions for ecologically responsible behaviour (ERB) and their perception of behavioural control (Liu et al., 2019). Furthermore, younger generations are more conscious of environmental concerns than older generations, indicating that age has a favourable impact on environmental views (Masud & Kari, 2015). The development of a reliable framework that accurately forecasts tourists' ERB while travelling remains a significant task (Cheng et al., 2021). ERB can help the environment and promote eco-friendly travel destinations. These results provide new evidence that visitor happiness has a favourable and significant impact on visitors' propensity to participate in environmentally conscious activities (Sahabuddin et al., 2024). This outcome demonstrates how community involvement may assist conservation groups in resolving tensions between enhancing local livelihoods and protecting the environment. Furthermore, travellers may believe that ecotourism execution is possible if they have more environmentally conscious views, which might encourage them to enhance their ecotourism behavioural intentions and engage in ecotourism activity (Lee & Jan, 2018). However, younger travellers will act more sustainably and engage in ecologically responsible activities to lessen their environmental impact when they have a more favourable opinion of the place (Fenitra et al., 2021). According to Wuxiang et al. (2022), travellers who have a favourable opinion of the quality of ecotourism are more likely to engage in proactive, environmentally conscious practices. However, frequent trips to green areas have the potential to improve people's perceptions of the environment and encourage more ecologically conscious behaviour. Thus, it is imperative to implement policies that provide people with

more opportunities to engage with nature (Kim et al., 2021).

5. Theoretical & Managerial Implications

The theoretical implication of the present study lies in understanding how TPB elements (environmental attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control), sustainability consciousness, environmental conservation, and anti-exceptionalism affect tourists' environmentally responsible behaviour for ecotourism. This study adds to the theory of planned behaviour (TPB) by showing how tourists influence their choices and behaviour regarding sustainability. The presence of anti-exceptionalism provides a critical viewpoint, urging travellers to behave responsibly and critically, rather than assuming ecotourism is constantly sustainable. However, scholars may investigate how these factors are related and how they all affect eco-friendly travel strategies in a better aspect, offering suggestions for better management and promotion of ecotourism. This study also emphasises the necessity for researchers to consider the wider social, cognitive, and ethical aspects of visitor behaviour, especially when it comes to environmental responsibility. This study provides a strong theoretical basis for further ecotourism research and for creating more potent interventions that promote long-term sustainability in the travel industry by concentrating on these intricate interdependencies. Academically, this study emphasises the value of a multifaceted approach to comprehending visitor behaviour and encourages greater research into how these components might be used to create effective plans for encouraging sustainable tourism practices.

This study offers valuable insights into improving ecotourism efficacy from a managerial perspective. Additionally, stakeholders such as site managers, marketers, and local authorities should prioritise gaining a thorough understanding of visitors' environmental attitudes, subjective norms, perceived behavioural control, sustainability consciousness, and environmental conservation. Furthermore, local communities and travel operators may promote societal norms that encourage sustainable behaviour, and marketing campaigns can highlight the significance of protecting natural resources. To improve the long-term sustainability of ecotourism efforts, stakeholders should raise the likelihood of responsible behaviour by highlighting sustainability consciousness and giving visitors information and resources so that they can make eco-friendly decisions. However, tourists' perception of control over responsible behaviour can also increase by providing valuable, easily accessible resources, such as eco-friendly transportation choices and garbage disposal facilities. Additionally, creating a zero-tolerance policy for unsustainable behaviour and reducing the acceptability of exceptionalism can assist in guaranteeing that visitors feel responsible for their environmental impact. Moreover, stakeholders may encourage sustainable, ecologically conscious behaviour by including these components in ecotourism initiatives, which will help the industry succeed and protect natural areas. By incorporating these concepts into ecotourism plans, stakeholders can promote greater community engagement, encourage

improved environmental practices, and ultimately support the growth of ecotourism as well as the preservation of natural areas. In addition, by providing stakeholders with a valuable framework for aligning their objectives with sustainable development, this framework fosters a win-win partnership between environmental preservation and tourism.

6. Conclusion and Future Research

This study integrates existing literature into a comprehensive framework that links the theory of planned behaviour (TPB), sustainability consciousness, environmental conservation, and anti-exceptionalism, which influence environmentally responsible behaviour in ecotourism. The framework suggests that TPB (environmental attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control) affects environmentally responsible behaviour. Furthermore, sustainability consciousness, which is influenced by knowledge of sustainable practices and awareness of environmental issues, promotes more responsible ecotourism behaviour. Environmental conservation is a crucial component that focuses on preserving biodiversity and ecosystems for future generations. Furthermore, travellers are more inclined to distribute Earth's resources, such as air, minerals, plants, land, water, and wildlife, if they believe that ecotourism should be critically assessed, just like any other sector, rather than being taken for granted as natural or advantageous. As a result, emphasising TPB aspects can improve travellers' attitudes and encourage ecotourism while promoting environmental preservation. In addition to raising the desire to travel to ecotourism destinations, these factors have an immense influence on environmentally conscious behaviour.

Additionally, future studies should empirically evaluate the suggested conceptual framework to learn more about the elements influencing travellers' environmentally conscious behaviour. By investigating the connections between TPB and other extended variables on eco-friendly behaviour, future studies can find ways to improve environmental value and satisfaction, which will ultimately support ecotourism's long-term growth.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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